

Management

A STUDY ON QUALITY OF WORKLIFE AMONG PRIVATE HOSPITAL NURSES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANNARKKAD MUNICIPALITY, PALAKKAD DISTRICT

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Abstract

In the life of a working individual, the quality of work life holds prime importance. Over a period of time, numerous opportunities have been created in the corporate world, each offering a more conducive work environment to the employee than the last. This has given rise to employee expectations, which coupled with the acceptance of the importance of employee retention, has forced employers to think even about the minutes of parameters which influence the quality of work life. Quality of nursing care is considered as an important aspect in evaluating the quality of health care. The quality of nursing and health care is directly interlinked to levels of job satisfaction among nurses and on the quality of nurse's work life. The rapidly changing health care environment has had an impact on the nursing work environment, workload and quality of nursing work life. In this paper studies the quality of work life among private hospital nurses.

Keywords: Quality of Work Life; Private Hospitals; Nurses.

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1. Introduction

In the life of a working individual, the quality of work life holds prime importance. Over a period of time, numerous opportunities have been created in the corporate world, each offering a more conducive work environment to the employee than the last. This has given rise to employee expectations, which coupled with the acceptance of the importance of employee retention, has forced employers to think even about the minutest of parameters which influence the quality of work life. Though the quality of work life has always been of paramount importance. For different industries, organizations and individuals there exist different set of factors, which influence the quality of work life and in turn motivate or de motivate the employees.

Quality of nursing care is considered as an important aspect in evaluating the quality of health care. The quality of nursing and health care is directly interlinked to levels of job satisfaction among nurses and on the quality of nurse's work life. The rapidly changing health care environment has had an impact on the nursing work environment, workload and quality of nursing work life. Studies have shown that work environment has an impact on the patient outcomes and nursing work life. Evidence shows that nursing shortage, poor quality of nurse's work life, job dissatisfaction and poor patient outcomes are directly linked to lack of healthy work environment.

2. Importance of Nurses in the Society

Nurses play a central role in delivering health care. Nurse's advocate for health promotion, educates patients and the public on the prevention of illness and injury, provide care and assist in cure, participate in rehabilitation, and provide support. No other health care professional such a broad and far-reaching role. Nurses help families learn to become healthy by helping them understand the range of emotional, physical, mental and cultural experiences they encounter during health and illness. Nurses help people and their families cope with illness, deal with it, and if necessary live with it, so that other parts of their lives can continue. Nurses do more than care for individuals. They have always have been at the forefront of change in health care and public health. Nurse provides ongoing assessment of people's health. Their round-the-clock presence, observation skills, and vigilance allow doctors to make better diagnoses and purpose better treatments. Many lives have been saved because an attentive nurse picked upon early warning signs of an upcoming crisis like cardiac arrest or respiratory failure.

3. Quality of Nursing Work Life

Job satisfaction was the most commonly conducted research in nursing. Job satisfaction mainly focuses on the likes and the dislikes of the employees and little interest is given to the work environment. Therefore problems related to the nursing work environment were not much addressed. Quality of work life was the concept which gained much acceptance in nursing. Numerous studies have been done to measure the quality of work life among nurses. Quality of work life provided a verity of definitions and predictors that influence the quality of work life among nurses. But there was a lack of uniformity in findings related to quality of work life.

3.1.Importance of Quality of Nursing Work Life

According to Brooks, the land mark studies done in work environment, work place and job satisfaction could make drastic improvements in nursing profession related to turnover and shortage. Majority of studies in nursing which evaluated job satisfaction was not able to make any enduring contributions in the nursing work environments. The profession still could not find appropriate explanations to the work life concerns of Clinical nurses.

Quality of Nursing Work Life is considered to be more effective since it is developed specifically to evaluate the work life of nursing. The concept of Quality of Nursing Work Life which is specific to nursing profession provides relevant and valuable information regarding the quality of work life among nurses. Brooks identified that no measures existed to assess the

quality of nursing work life specifically. This gap in the evidence compelled her to develop an instrument in quality of nursing work life.

4. Objectives

- 1) To analyze the quality of work life of nurses working in private hospitals in Mannarkkad municipality Palakkad District.
- 2) To analyze the variables which influence the quality of work life at work place on nurses.
- 3) To identify the importance of work environment towards the performance of nurses.
- 4) To know which extend the nurses able to balance their work life with personal life.
- 5) To know salary level, approach of superior work load, quality of work Environment.

5. Scope and Significant of the Study

Quality of Work Life has emerged as one of the most important aspects of job that ensures long term association of employees with the organization. It is essential for the organization to develop quality relation between its employees and working environment because now-a-days, demanding of job creates imbalance between family and work life due to job pressure and conflicting interests.

Healthcare sector, being one of the largest service sector employers today is also not spared from the dreaded evil of 'attrition'. The employees have certain expectations from such institutions too. And, if not fulfilled, new opportunities are there to poach away such talented employees. Hence, it is very important that the management of the healthcare institutions too tighten their seat belts and probe deep to understand such areas which when catered to will help in attracting new talent and retaining them. The present study deals with some important aspects of quality of work life among private hospital nurses

6. Collection of Data

The data is collected through primary and secondary sources.

- **Primary data**

Primary data was collected from the respondents using structured questionnaires, which was prepared in such a way that, it enables the respondent to express their opinion freely and frankly and collect data from 150 respondents.

- **Secondary data**

Secondary data was collected from different published and unpublished research reports, text books, magazine, journals, articles, website etc.

7. Tools of Analysis

- Simple percentage analysis
- z-test
- ANOVA
- Garrett ranking technique
- Correlation

8. Limitations

- Sample size is limited to 150 nurses.
- There may be errors due to the bias of the respondents.
- Due to time constraints and busy schedule of nurses, it was difficult to interact with them completely.
- The study is limited to nurses in Mannarkkad municipality. There for the findings of the study cannot be extended to other areas.

9. Review of Literature

S.Khodadadi et al (2014)²⁷ investigated the QWL dimensions effect on the employees' job satisfaction. In this study independent variables were permanent security providing, salary and benefits payment policies, development and promotion opportunity, and job independence, job satisfaction as the dependent variables. 114 employees selected randomly for this study and two questionnaires of "quality of work life" and "job satisfaction" was used for data collection and Data analysis was done by using SPSS and LISREL software. He founded out that the salary and benefits' policies have a significant and positive effect on Shuhstar's Shohola Hospital employees' job satisfaction.

Dr.O.P. Singh and Sandeep kumar singh, (2015)²⁸ observed on quality of work life if teachers working in higher educational institution: A strategic approach towards teacher's excellence. He founded that quality of work life is an important issue from the teacher's perspective as it effect the job satisfaction level, commitment, performance and performance level. he also suggest that higher educational authority should take progressive step to organize a conductive and congenial work cultural and environmental at higher educational level in which every teacher works in a well-defined manner for their own excellence and for institutional effective also.

MD.Inamual Haque, MD Suhail Rana and Zainal abedin (2015)²⁹ stated on assessing the quality of work life of garment works in Bangladesh, a study on garment industries in Dhaka city. They founded out that quality of work life has dominant role in garment industry. He also suggests that give importance to ensure good health and safety efforts from employers.

Dr yogesh jain and renil Thomas (2016)³⁰ he studied on quality of work life among the employees of a leading pharmaceutical limited company of Vadodara district. He founded that there exist a relationship between organizational commitment and other four components of quality of work life. He suggests that the company must devise the policy on career advancement and career positioning for better inflow of knowledge. He also suggest that company must do away the traditional method of advancing an employee purely on the basis of seniority even if better talent on the basis of performance is available, else company will start facing the elevation of labour turnover problem at the earliest.

10. Walton Model of Quality of Work Life

The other approach to QWL is provided by Walton (1973). Walton proposes an ideal quality of work life programme which will include practices in eight major areas as discussed below:

Walton Model of Quality of Work Life

11. Analysis and Interpretations

Table 1: showing the Level of Quality of Work Life

Quality of work Life	Frequency	Percentage
Low(17-42)	44	29.3
Moderate(43-49)	60	40.0
High (50-85)	46	30.7
	150	100.0

Chart 1: showing the Level of Quality of Work Life

Interpretation

It is found from the table that 29.3% of the respondents have low level of quality of work life, 40% of the respondents have moderate level of quality of work life and remaining 30.7% of the respondents have high level of quality of work life.

Table 2: showing correlation between stress and quality of work life

Correlation			
		Total Quality of work life	
Stress level	Pearson correlation	1	.128
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.117
	N	150	150
Total Quality of Work life	Pearson correlation	.128	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.117	
	N	150	150

Interpretation

To find out the relationship between the level of stress and Quality of Work Life correlation was done. The p value (.117) is greater than .05 so there is no significant relationship between stress and quality of work life.

12. Findings

- Majority of the respondents are faced high level of stress
- Majority of 40% of the respondents have moderate level of quality of work life.
- Ranking of major motivational factors salary is ranked first, convenient shift is ranked second, good working condition is ranked third, job security is ranked fourth and other incentives are ranked fifth.
- The p value (.000) is less than .05. so there is significant mean difference in the quality of work life based on gender of the respondent.
- The p value (.000) is less than .05. So there is significant mean difference in the quality of work life based on marital status of the respondent.

13. Suggestions

- The organisation can provide regular medical checkup for improving the medical facilities.
- The organisation can provide effective training for efficient performance of employees.
- The organisation can improve promotional policies
- Provide substantial freedom, independence and discretion to employees in scheduling their work.
- Team culture, peer relations also influence the quality of work life of the employees. So there should be good relationship between employees.

14. Conclusion

The study was done to determine the quality of nursing work life among nurses working in Mannarkkad municipality, Palakkad district. The study findings revealed that there was a moderate quality of nursing work life reported among nurses in private sector. The work environment of the nurses was given least importance and they were compelled to manage with limited resources. Even though the nurses in the private sector reported lesser work load, they were more dissatisfied with salary and financial benefits. The salary in the private sector was significantly lower.

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